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Brown juice assisted ensiling of straw and press cake for enhanced biogas production and nutrient availability in digestates

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effects of ensiling and brown juice-assisted ensiling of wheat straw and press cake from a green biorefinery plant prior to anaerobic co-digestion (Aco-D) with cattle manure on methane yield and nutrient availability in the digestates. Straw was ensiled with and without brown juice at field-scale and lab-scale levels, followed by Aco-D with manure using continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTR) and batch tests. The digestates from CSTR were incorporated into the soil to study nitrogen and sulphur dynamics and availability over 80 days. Results show that ensiling of straw increased net inorganic nitrogen release in soil and reduced net inorganic sulphur immobilisation compared to the non-ensiled straw. Brown juice-assisted ensiling of straw at the lab-scale level significantly increased methane production by 14 % and increased hydrolysis and methane production rates compared to non-ensiled straw. These results demonstrate that ensiling of straw has the potential as a pre-treatment technique for enhanced biogas production and higher nutrient availability in digestates for crop production and provides an opportunity to valorise brown juice as an ensiling additive.

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1. Introduction

Cereal straw is an abundant by-product of agricultural production and has received considerable attention as a globally available feedstock that could be valorised into different valuable products (Björnsson and Prade, 2021). The straw has been identified as a promising feedstock for bioenergy production in anaerobic digestion (AD). The utilisation of straw for biogas production reduces dependency on other feedstock's resulting in more efficient use of agricultural land (Ambye-Jensen et al., 2013). Additionally, anaerobic co-digestion of cereal straw with livestock manure results in AD system optimisation and improvement of the economic viability of the biogas plants as it increases biogas production and provides an option to recycle and re-use nutrients from straw (Sørensen et al., 2019). Generally, the AD process results in a digestate

Abbreviations: AD, anaerobic digestion; Aco-D, anaerobic co-digestion; CSTR, continuous stirred-tank reactor; LAB, lactic acid bacteria; BJ, brown juice; TAN, total ammoniacal nitrogen; VFA, volatile fatty acids; BMP, biochemical methane potential; Co-dig, co-digested; NDSF, neutral detergent soluble fibre

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characterised with a high NH_4^+ /total N ratio due to the mineralisation of organically bound N, making it an alternative to substitute synthetic fertilisers in agriculture (Møller and Müller, 2012). Furthermore, the degradation of the substrate's organic matter during the complex biochemical reactions of AD results in thinner digestate characterised with low dry matter content, which enhances better soil infiltration and minimises microbial immobilisation of nutrients when applied to the soil.

After cereal crop harvesting, straw is either left in the field and incorporated into the soil or collected for fodder, bedding materials, building materials, biomaterials or incineration at heating plants (Bakker et al., 2013; Fjortoft et al., 2019). However, continuous removal of straw from fields may cause fertility depletion due to reduced soil organic carbon and increased risk of soil erosion. Additionally, direct incorporation into the soil can negatively influence crop growth due to its slow degradation (Li et al., 2022). Using straw for biogas and the resultant digestate, a by-product, to fertilise the crops can counteract the adverse effects of removing the straw from the field and their effect on direct incorporation. This process is more economical and sustainable, especially with a short distance between the field and the biogas plant facility due to the high costs associated with straw collection, handling and transport.

Despite the benefits and potential of the straw for biogas production, its efficient utilisation as a feedstock for AD faces numerous challenges (Ai et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019). The crystallinity of the straw's cellulose and lignin content limits the degradation of the lignocellulosic structure during AD, as the decomposable components, such as carbohydrates and other macromolecules, are protected (Mancini et al., 2018). The protection subsequently limits microbial and enzymatic attack during the hydrolysis stage of AD (Mirmohamadsadeghi et al., 2021), resulting in lower biogas yields and high dry matter content in the digestate due to incomplete degradation. The high dry matter content negatively influences the fertiliser value of the digestates and their management during storage and field application (Fontaine et al., 2020). It induces nutrient immobilisation, increases ammonia volatilisation if digestate is surface applied and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions due to high residual methane potential (Møller et al., 2022). Therefore, efficient pre-treatment of straw prior to AD targeted to reduce the degree of polymerisation and crystallinity to facilitate enzymatic and microbial hydrolysis is required to optimise the AD process for enhanced biogas production and nutrient solubilisation in the digestates.

Several pre-treatment methods of straw for AD have been studied based on their mechanisms of action on the substrate, such as chemical (i.e. alkaline, acid hydrolysis), biological (i.e. use of enzymes, composting), physical (i.e. electrokinetic, milling, extrusion) or a combination of all the techniques (Atege et al., 2020). These techniques have shown effectiveness in changing substrates' properties and improving biogas yields, but their usage and upscaling are limited due to the cost incurred and their energy consumption (Harris and McCabe, 2015; Larsen et al., 2017). Alternative pre-treatment techniques, which are cost-effective and environmentally friendly, such as ensiling and co-ensiling, have been exploited to treat straw prior to anaerobic digestion (Feng et al., 2020, 2019; Larsen et al., 2017; Sieborg et al., 2020). For instance, Feng et al. (2018) investigated the effect of co-ensiling of cover crops and barley straw and found that co-ensiling blends had advantages over cover crops as they elevated hydrolysis rates and decreased lag phase. Similarly, Larsen et al. (2017) found that co-ensiling wheat with sugar beet leaves increased biochemical methane potential from 19 to 34 % at the lab-scale level after co-ensiling for nine months and 18 to 32 % after six months of co-ensiling at pilot scale. These studies focused only on the effects of the ensiling as a pre-treatment technique on biogas yields, with a limited focus on the effect on nutrient availability in digestates and their dynamics in soil. During ensiling, organic acids are produced, which act as acid catalysts to break ester bonds of lignocellulosic biopolymers and break the biomass's waxy hydrophobic surfaces, enhancing substrate degradation during AD (Larsen et al., 2017). However, ensiling pure agricultural cereal straw such as wheat straw poses challenges due to low fermentable sugar and low water content to enhance lactic acid fermentation required to lower substrates' pH (Sieborg et al., 2020).

Some of the strategies to improve ensiling of these kinds of lignocellulosic biomass include; adding appropriate levels of water, adding fermentable sugars to promote the growth of *Lactobacillus*, inoculation of straw with a lactic acid bacteria (LAB) culture and decrease of substrate's pH by addition of organic acids (Ambye-Jensen et al., 2013). Alternatively, ensiling of straw could be enhanced by the use of additives. Additives act as fermentation stimulators which favour lactic acid fermentation by supplying fermentable sugars, LAB or enzymes (McDonald et al., 1991). Yang et al. (2006) investigated the effects of adding glucose to adjust initial water-soluble carbohydrates on silage fermentation of straw and found that high doses of glucose (7 to 10 % DM) compared to low doses achieved a better silage quality. Furthermore, Ambye-Jensen et al. (2013) found a better silage quality with only 0.35 % loss in total DM and pH change from 7.0 to 3.7 after adding xylose and heterofermentative LAB inoculum to wheat straw prior to ensiling. The fermentation stimulators can be commercially or locally available such as brown juice. Brown juice, a waste product from green biorefinery after extracting protein concentrate from grass, is a sugar-rich brown liquid with low pH associated with lactic acid fermentation (Feng et al., 2021).

The brown juice has no known economic value as mono-digestion in biogas plants yields low biogas quantities and is also characterised by a low fertiliser value (Santamaria-Fernandez et al., 2020). Additionally, the direct disposal of brown juice poses environmental challenges in the biorefinery process due to its high biological oxygen demand and sugar contents (Bákonny et al., 2020). Hence utilising brown juice as an additive in the ensiling of the biomass, where its addition provides; adequate moisture, sugars, and a lower pH environment for forming organic acids, i.e. lactic, citric and succinic acids, may provide valuable and economic benefits.

The anaerobic co-digestion of ensiled substrates with manure combines two complex biochemical processes that might have positive or negative synergetic effects. Therefore, the brown juice-assisted ensiling of biomass and its subsequent

effect on biomethanation and nutrient solubilisation in AD ought to be studied. To effectively utilise nutrients in resultant digestates, i.e. N and S, to replace mineral fertilisers, the application has to be done in synchrony with plant demand, and this demands a thorough understanding of the nutrients dynamics following the application of digestates to the soil as they undergo mineralisation and immobilisation processes concurrently (Delin and Engström, 2010; Eriksen, 2005).

In this study, we evaluated the effects of ensiling and brown juice-assisted ensiling of straw and press cake as an alternative pre-treatment method on methane production and the nitrogen and sulphur availability following the application of digestates to the soil. Brown juice was added to the biomasses, and ensiling was done at both lab- and field-scale levels, followed by a co-digestion with cattle manure. This is the first study to evaluate the effects of brown juice-assisted ensiling of straw for anaerobic digestion on N and S dynamics and availability in the soil. We hypothesised that ensiling of substrates would enhance the anaerobic digestion process, increasing net inorganic N release in the soil from the digestates while reducing inorganic S immobilisation in soil.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Substrates

Winter wheat straw (*Triticum aestivum* L.) for lab-scale ensiling was obtained from a field near Thisted, Denmark, which was harvested on 12th August 2020, and the straw was baled three days later without any precipitation. The straw was coarsely chopped with the integrated chopper in the baler to achieve a 5–15 cm size. Wheat straw for field-scale ensiling was obtained from a field near Hanstholm in Denmark, which was harvested on 16th August 2020, and the straw was exposed to considerable precipitation before baling on 9th September. The press cake and brown juice were obtained from the demonstration-scale green biorefinery plant at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, following crude protein extraction from the grass as described by Feng et al. (2021). The washed grass is screw pressed, separating a green juice and a fibrous press cake. The crude protein is precipitated by heating the green juice at 80 °C, followed by centrifugation to separate the protein concentrate and residual brown juice. The brown juice is then cooled and stored in tanks until use.

The brown juice used for lab-scale ensiling was from red clover and high-sugar grass, and it contained 4.2 g kg⁻¹ total sugars, 2.36 g kg⁻¹ lactic acids, 0.1 g kg⁻¹ acetic acids, 2.5 % dry matter (DM), 80 % volatile solids in DM, 0.2 % ash content in DM and pH of 4.56. The fermented brown juice and press cake were stored at -18 °C prior to their use in the experimental setup. The brown juice for field-scale ensiling was produced from *Festulolium* grass and was stored in a tank at ambient temperature for four weeks before the ensiling experiment. It contained 30.7 g kg⁻¹ organic matter, 25.6 g kg⁻¹ lactic acid in fresh matter (FM), 4.6 g kg⁻¹ of acetic acid, 2.21 g kg⁻¹ of total sugars, and a pH of 3.80. Cattle manure used for the co-digestion experiment was obtained from the animal facilities at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, whereby a small amount of wheat straw was used as a bedding material. It was subdivided into small portions and frozen until used in the digesters.

2.2. Ensiling of biomass with- and without brown juice

2.2.1. Field-scale ensiling of wheat straw

In the field-scale ensiling, wet wheat straw was baled with a New Holland baler (type BB960R) with an integrated coarse chopper, producing bales with dimensions of 90 × 120 × 175 cm and a weight of approximately 350 kg in FM. Straw was either baled without any ensiling additive (Straw_{fieldsilage}) or with brown juice as an ensiling additive (straw + BJ_{fieldsilage}). The brown juice was sprayed directly onto the straw just in front of the pick-up on the baler, and the juice was dosed using a system developed for adding sulphuric acid to liquid manure to avoid ammonia evaporation during the application at the rate of 76 kg brown juice ton⁻¹ FM (Table S1). After baling, the straw bales were wrapped with eight layers of plastic folio (Scan Farm Tornado) and stored at ambient temperature for ensiling for 211 days.

On 8th April 2021, the two bales were opened, and approx. 50 kg of fresh weight was sampled from each bale, and the straw silage was mechanically chopped to attain a 1–2 cm length for use in continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTR) and batch AD experiments. Non-ensiled straw, hereby referred to as Straw_{field}, was used as a reference during AD.

2.2.2. Lab-scale ensiling

Straw for lab-scale ensiling was shredded to attain a 1–2 cm length using a quad shaft shredder UNTHA RS 30 4-S (Kuchl, Australia) and stored in plastic bags. Brown juice was manually added to the shredded straw in a ratio of 1:1 based on fresh weight, equivalent to a dosage of 1000 kg brown juice ton⁻¹ straw FM, and mixed homogeneously by an Atika 145S mixer (Viborg, Denmark). Next, tap water was added to adjust the dry matter to around 30–35 % in straw, appropriate for silage making. The mixing was done in portions of 3 kg to ensure proper mixing. For the press cake, brown juice was added in a ratio of 2:1 to achieve a dry matter content of around 30 %. The straw and press cake mixed with brown juice were then ensiled using a vacuum-based plastic bag system. They were packed in plastic bags (3–4 kg each), air removed by a vacuum machine (Supermax INGVALD™, Denmark), and then stored at room temperature for three months, resulting in silage hereafter referred to as straw + BJ_{labsilage} and Press cake + BJ_{labsilage}. At the end of 90 days of ensiling, the silage bags were frozen at -18 °C until CSTR digestion and batch tests were commenced.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the field- and lab-scale ensiling of straw and anaerobic digestion process in batch and continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTR) at thermophilic conditions (51 °C).

Straw mixed with brown juice and not ensiled, hereafter referred to as straw + BJ_{lab} and straw without brown juice and not ensiled, hereafter referred to as straw_{lab} were used as references during AD (Fig. 1). Representative sub-samples of ensiled and non-ensiled substrates were taken to analyse dry matter (DM), volatile solids (VS), ash content, pH, volatile fatty acids (VFA), totals sugars, acetic acid and lactic acid.

2.3. Anaerobic digestion

2.3.1. Lab-scale continuous anaerobic digestion experiment

The ensiled (straw + BJ_{Labsilage}, Straw_{fieldsilage}, Straw + BJ_{fieldsilage} and Press cake + BJ_{labsilage}) and non-ensiled (Straw + BJ_{Lab}, Straw_{field} and Press cake) substrates were co-digested with cattle manure using laboratory scale CSTR with a working volume of 15 L (Fig. 1). Before start-up, the reactors were filled with a de-gassed inoculum for a week and operated at thermophilic conditions (51 °C) to allow the AD microbes to adapt and check the reactors' leakage. The inoculum was obtained from a 1200 m³ full-scale biogas plant at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, which had been running with cattle manure and a proportion of grass, straw and maize silage as the primary substrate for over one year at thermophilic conditions (51 °C).

After the start-up period, each reactor was manually fed daily with a mixture of cattle manures and substrates (ensiled or non-ensiled) and one reactor was used for mono-digestion of cattle manure as a control to investigate effects on nutrient availability. An equivalent amount of the digestate was offloaded daily by gravity from the discharge tube at the bottom of the reactors to maintain a constant volume. The substrates were fed with an organic loading rate (OLR) of 3.0–3.3 g⁻¹ VS⁻¹ L⁻¹ day⁻¹ and a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 25 days. The reactors were mechanically mixed throughout the experiment at 60 revolutions per minute and heated by heating mats fitted outside the reactor. The reactors' temperature was monitored and controlled using temperature probes.

Daily biogas yields after feeding substrates were recorded automatically using Ritter drum-type gas metres, TG 05 models (Dr.-Ing RITTER Apparatebau GMBH & Co KG) and gas composition was analysed weekly to quantify methane yield. Two cattle slurry types, henceforth called cattle manure, were collected at different times, with contrasting characteristics, and were used in an anaerobic co-digestion with substrates (Table 2). Raw cattle manure 1 (CM1) was used in the co-digestion of field-scale ensiled substrates, while cattle manure 2 (CM2) was used in the co-digestion of lab-scale ensiled substrates. Digestates from the reactors were collected weekly to analyse pH, DM content, VS, volatile fatty acids (VFA) and total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN). The experiment was conducted for 75 days, corresponding to three HRTs, to ensure the stability of the reactors' performance at the end of the experiment. At the end of the lab-scale anaerobic digestion, the CSTRs were emptied manually into 20 L buckets, sub-samples were taken for analysis, and the rest of the digestates were stored at –18 °C pending a soil incubation experiment.

2.3.2. Biochemical methane potential (BMP) of straw

The BMP of the ensiled and non-ensiled straw was determined using batch assays at thermophilic conditions (51 °C) using the procedure suggested by Moset et al. (2015). A de-gassed inoculum, pre-incubated for two weeks at thermophilic temperature to deplete degradable organic matter, was utilised. The inoculum was sourced from a full-scale reactor at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, running at thermophilic conditions (51 °C). The inoculum was characterised by 3.5 % DM content, a volatile solid proportion of 2.2 %, an ash content of 1.27 %, NH₄⁺-N content of 1.41 g kg⁻¹ and a pH of 7.91. Triplicate bottles were filled with 200 g of inoculum, and the corresponding amount of substrate was added to achieve an inoculum-substrate ratio of 1:1 based on the volatile solids. Bottles containing only the inoculum were filled and used as blank samples to measure endogenous biogas production. The bottles were sealed with rubber stoppers and

screw caps, and then the headspace was purged with N₂ gas for two minutes to create anaerobic conditions. The bottles were then incubated at thermophilic conditions (51 °C) for 90 days.

Biogas yield was measured by inserting a needle attached to a tube with an inlet into a column filled with acidified water (pH < 2) through a butyl rubber cap and was calculated by the volume of water displaced. Biogas yields and compositions were measured at day intervals until day 90. The methane production from each substrate was corrected by subtracting the endogenous biogas production volume of the inoculum. The gas composition was analysed using gas chromatography (Agilent technologies 7890A, CA 95051, USA) coupled with a thermal conductivity detector and helium gas, a carrier gas. The measured CH₄ content was corrected as a proportion of biogas's CH₄ + CO₂ contents. The specific methane yields were normalised to standard conditions (0 °C and 1.013 bars).

2.4. Soil incubation experiment

The digestates from CSTR digestion were amended to the soil in an incubation experiment to study their N and S dynamics and availability. The soil was collected from the top plough layer (0–20 cm) from an arable field at Aarhus University, Research Centre Foulum, Denmark (56°30'N, 09°35'E). The soil is a loamy sand with 83 g clay kg⁻¹, 284 g silt kg⁻¹, 610 g sand kg⁻¹, 31 g organic matter kg⁻¹, 1.3 g total N kg⁻¹, 15.6 g total C kg⁻¹ and pH (1:2.5 H₂O) of 6.51. Air-dried soil was sieved through a < 2 mm sieve to remove stones and larger plant residues, homogenised and then pre-incubated at 10 °C until the start of the experiment.

Approximately 50 g of the soil based on the dry matter weight was weighed into a 250 ml polyethylene bottle, and then the organic materials (digestates and cattle manures) were added at the rate of 200 mg N kg⁻¹ soil, followed by another 50 g equivalent of dry soil to cover the digestates. A non-amended soil was included as a control, and another soil was amended with ammonium sulphate at 100 mg N kg⁻¹ soil as a reference treatment. The application rate of the digestates and cattle manures is equivalent to 180 kg N ha⁻¹, assuming a 7-cm layer of soil is affected by the organic addition in the field (Sørensen et al., 2003). Water was added to each bottle to achieve a moisture level equivalent to 55 % of the water holding capacity (WHC), optimal for microbial activity and low enough to limit denitrification. The bottles were covered with hole-pierced parafilm to prevent high water loss through evaporation while ensuring aeration during the incubation period. Each treatment was replicated 21 times to allow three replicates to be destructively sampled for analysis on days 0, 2, 7, 14, 28, 50 and 80 (Table 4).

The samples were incubated at 10 °C in a dark room, representing the average, typical soil temperature in spring under field conditions in Denmark when digestates/slurries are applied. The soil moisture content was monitored every two weeks and adjusted based on the initial weights. On each sampling day, the soil was removed from the polyethylene containers, homogenised in aluminium trays, and portions of it (25 g) extracted with 100 ml of 1M KCL solution to extract inorganic N (NO₃⁻-N, NO₂⁻-N and exchangeable NH₄⁺-N). Another portion (25 g) was extracted with 50 ml of 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution for extraction of inorganic S (SO₄²⁻-S) by mechanical shaking for a half-hour (end-over-end). Extracts were frozen at -18 °C until analyses. Soil pH (in 0.01 M CaCl₂ extracts) and soil moisture content were also measured.

2.5. Analytical methods

Dry matter, volatile solids and ash contents in substrates and digestates were analysed according to the standard methods (APHA, 2005). The dry matter was determined by drying the samples to a constant weight at 80 °C. Volatile solids and ash were determined by loss on ignition at 550 °C for 6 h. The dry matter and volatile solids of the silage substrates were corrected for volatile compounds lost during oven drying, as proposed by Weizbach and Strubelt (2008). Total N in the cattle manures and digestates was analysed according to APHA (2005) by the Kjeldahl digestion method (Kjeltec™ 8400, Foss Analytical CO. LTD, Denmark). Ammonium-nitrogen was analysed using an automated distillation-titration method (Sommer et al., 1992) using a Gerhardt Vapodest 10 s distillation apparatus (Bonn, Germany). Sample preparation for fibre analysis entailed drying the samples at 60 °C for 48 h and grinding them to 0.8 mm particle size using Cyclotec™ 1093 mill (Foss, MN 55344, USA).

Acid detergent fibre (ADF), acid detergent lignin (ADL) and neutral detergent fibre (NDF) in ensiled and non-ensiled substrates were analysed to determine the hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin and neutral detergent soluble fibre (NDSF) contents as described by Van Soest et al. (1991), using a Foss Fibertec 2010 System (Foss Analytical CO. LTD, Denmark). Hemicellulose was calculated as the difference between NDF and ADF, cellulose as the difference between ADF and ADL; lignin content was assumed to be equivalent to ADL, and NDSF was estimated as the difference between 100% and % NDF. Total carbon content was analysed by Dumas combustion method using an elemental analyser (Vario MAX Cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH). Elementary analysis of the substrates was conducted to determine C, H, N, O and S atomic contents using a CHNS elemental analyser (Vario MACRO cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH).

The pH, volatile fatty acids, Lactic acids and NH₄⁺-N contents in the straw and press cake silage were determined in a water filtrate obtained by extracting 2 g of the substrate with 40 ml of distilled water using a laboratory mixer as described by Feng et al. (2018). Volatile fatty acids were analysed using 7890A gas chromatography equipped with a flame ionisation detector (Agilent Technologies, CA 95051, USA), while Lactic acid was measured using Agilent 1100 liquid chromatography equipped with a refractive index detector (Agilent Technologies, CA 95051, USA) and a ROA-organic acid H+ ion exclusion column (Phenomenex, CA 90501, USA), running at a temperature of 80 °C.

The soil filtrates' inorganic N (NO_3^- -N, NO_2^- -N and exchangeable NH_4^+ -N) were analysed by Auto Analyser AA500 flow colourimetry (Seal Analytical GmbH, Germany). Total sulphur in the digestates and cattle manure was determined by turbidimetry after wet ashing with magnesium nitrate and perchloric acid (Eriksen et al., 2008), whereas total sulphide and total sulphate were analysed in a zinc acetate-sample solution prepared as per the procedure described by Eriksen et al. (2008). In addition, sulphate in 0.01 M CaCl_2 soil extracts from the incubation experiment was analysed by turbidimetry by precipitating the sulfates with barium chloride and acidifying with hydrochloric acid (Eriksen et al., 2008).

2.6. Calculations

The net inorganic N release in the soil as a percentage of total N applied from the organic inputs was estimated as the difference between the total inorganic N (TIN) in the amended soils with treatments and control soil without any amendment divided by total N in the organic inputs according to Eq. (1):

$$\text{Net inorganic N release (\% of N input)} = \frac{\text{TIN}_{\text{Treatment}} - \text{TIN}_{\text{Reference}}}{\text{TN}_{\text{Applied}}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Denitrification and nitrous oxide losses from the soils after digestates incorporation were assumed to be negligible or similar from all the treatments applied. Clay fixation of ammonium-N was equally assumed to be negligible. Net inorganic S (SO_4^{2-} -S) release in soil was calculated similarly to net inorganic N release as per Eq. (1). Net inorganic N mineralisation after 80 days of incubation was calculated as the difference in the net inorganic N release (NiNrelease) at day 80 and net inorganic N release at day 0 as shown in Eq. (2):

$$\text{N mineralisation (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{NiNrelease}_{\text{day80}} - \text{NiNrelease}_{\text{day0}} \quad (2)$$

The measured biochemical methane potential in batch tests was modelled as a function of time by fitting the measured experimental data using two non-linear regression models with the solver function of Microsoft Excel[®] Tool Pak. The first model is the modified Gompertz model as described by (Lo et al., 2010), Eq. (3):

$$B = B_0 \exp \left\{ -\exp \left[\frac{\mu_m e}{B_0} (\lambda - t) + 1 \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where B is cumulative specific methane yield ($\text{mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1}$) at time t (day), B_0 is the ultimate methane potential ($\text{mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1}$); and μ_m is the maximum methane production ($\text{mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$), λ is the lag phase time (days), which is the minimum time necessary to produce CH_4 or bacteria to acclimatise, t is the incubation time (days), and e is the Euler's number (2.7183). The second model used was a first-order kinetic model proposed by Hashimoto (1989), as per Eq. (4). This model assumes hydrolysis to be the rate-limiting step in the AD process:

$$B = B_0 (1 - \exp^{-kt}) \quad (4)$$

where B is cumulative specific methane yield ($\text{mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1}$) at time t (day), B_0 is the ultimate methane potential (BMP_{90}) at 90 days ($\text{mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1}$); and k is the methane production rate constant per day (degradation potential). The constant k is substrate-specific, giving information about the time required to achieve a certain fraction of B_0 (Feng et al., 2018). The specific methane yields ($\text{NL CH}_4 \text{ kg VS}^{-1}$) from the CSTR digestion experiment were calculated as the average in the last HRT of 25 days, where a steady state had been achieved.

2.7. Statistical analysis

The effects of ensiling as a pre-treatment technique and anaerobic digestion on net inorganic N and S release in the soil following the application of digestates were evaluated by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using R statistical software (version 4.0.3). The pre-treatment effects were evaluated on field-scale and lab-scale ensiled substrates separately as they were co-digested with two types of cattle manures and straws with distinct characteristics. A Tukey HSD test was performed to identify treatments that were significantly different. Shapiro-Wilk tests, quantile-quantile plots and visual examination of the residuals against the fitted values were performed to confirm normality and homoscedasticity assumptions in the data. In cases where data deviated from the normal distribution, statistical analysis was performed on the log-transformed data.

Pearson's correlation coefficients were used to assess the correlations between net inorganic N and S release in the soil with biochemical characteristics of the digestates. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used for all statistical tests.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effects of ensiling on the chemical composition of substrates

The characteristics of the ensiled and non-ensiled straw and press cake are summarised in Table 1. The straw and press cake used for lab-scale ensiling had a dry matter content of 88 % and 38 %, respectively, which was reduced after

ensiling. Lab-scale ensiling of straw and press cake with brown juice (Straw+BJ_{lab silage} and press cake+BJ_{lab silage}) resulted in a 4 to 6 % dry matter loss. Addition of brown juice to straw without ensiling led to a drop in pH by 0.7 units and a further decline of 2.9 units after 90 days of lab-scale ensiling. For press cake, the pH dropped slightly by 0.9 units after ensiling.

Lab-scale ensiling of straw with brown juice resulted in low pH levels (3.81) and higher lactic acid and acetic acid concentrations of 21.3 g kg⁻¹ in FM and 3.1 g kg⁻¹ in FM, respectively and no butyric acid (Table 1). The silage met the criterion for good silage quality, i.e. with pH < 4.5, lactic acid yield > 30 g kg⁻¹ DM and butyric acid < 10 % of total VFA (Feng et al., 2019; Pahlou et al., 2003).

The good quality of lab-scale ensiled straw could be ascribed to the size of the straw, appropriate moisture content and the brown juice acting as a fermentation stimulator. In lab-scale ensiling, contrary to the field-scale ensiling, straw was chopped to 1–2 cm in length, enabling a higher packing density, lower porosity and less air penetration to the silage reducing aerobic deterioration risk at feed-out (Franco et al., 2016). This reduces both biomass spoilage and losses. Furthermore, adding the brown juice as a fermentation stimulator and adjusting the dry matter content to around 30 % before ensiling may have provided multiple synergistic effects compared to field-scale ensiled straw, which had a higher initial DM content (Table 1). First, by providing a conducive environment for bacterial growth and acting as a source of carbohydrates to the lactic acid bacteria population, enhancing lactic acid fermentation. Second, the high dosage of brown juice (ratio 1:1) compared to that used in field ensiling (Table S1) could have potentially compensated for a poor fermenting straw, improving its silage quality.

The decline in pH during ensiling is associated with organic acids and antimicrobial peptides produced by the lactic acid bacteria-induced fermentation process (Kung et al., 2018). The pH development of the field-scale ensiled straw was monitored during the ensiling period, and it decreased to around pH 5 and to pH 4.7 after 124 and 211 days of ensiling, respectively (Table S1). The higher pH, higher dry matter content and relatively low levels of organic acids, volatile fatty acids and total sugars observed in field-scale ensiled straw may be attributed to either air penetration to the silage at the sub-sampling point, air exposure during storage of sampled straw and chopping of ensiled straw before anaerobic co-digestion (Table 1). The chopping of ensiled straw may have exposed the fermented straw to air resulting in a loss of readily available carbohydrates and volatile fatty acids. However, butyric acids were not detected in any of the ensiled samples.

Hemicellulose was lower in ensiled straw than in non-ensiled straw and reduced by 24 % and 12 % in the field- and lab-scale ensiled straw, respectively, while it was reduced by 8 % in press cake (Table 1). The reductions were consistent with reductions in dry matter and volatile solids content (Table 1). The reduction of hemicellulose is enhanced by the organic acids formed throughout the ensiling process (Ambye-Jensen et al., 2013). Additionally, it could be linked to its amorphous structure with lower polymerisation compared to cellulose and lignin (Larsen et al., 2017). The hemicellulose degradation positively affects the silage fermentation process and, ultimately, has a subsequent effect on biogas production, as seen in this study. Feng et al. (2019) observed similar effects on hemicellulose in a straw and cover crops co-ensiling experiment.

On the other hand, the cellulose and lignin concentration in DM remained constant or slightly increased (Table 1) during the ensiling period, probably due to the disappearance of easily degradable organic matter and also due to the phenolic rigidity of lignin, which acts as a physical barrier to degradation (Larsen et al., 2017). Similar effects on cellulose and lignin were reported in previous studies (Feng et al., 2018, 2019; Fjortoft et al., 2019). The neutral detergent soluble fibre increased with ensiling, and the most considerable effect was observed in lab-scale ensiling, where there was an increase of 8 % points (Table 1). The breakdown of hemicellulose and increased neutral soluble fibre content during ensiling could explain the increased nutrient availability after anaerobic digestion.

Lab-scale ensiling tended to increase the extractable ammonium nitrogen and decrease the C/N ratio in the substrates (Table 1). The presence of appropriate moisture content and sugars in straw could explain this by enhancing protein hydrolysis during the fermentation process (Kung et al., 2018). Our results are consistent with those of Xia et al. (2018), who found a higher concentration of NH₄-N/total N in whole-crop wheat after adding 6 % molasses, which they attributed to proteolysis during ensiling.

3.2. Effects of anaerobic digestion on manure characteristics

The chemical characteristics of the digestates and cattle manures used in the incubation experiment are summarised in Table 2. The dry matter content ranged from 3.5 to 7.2 %, with the lowest being in digested cattle manure 1 (CM1) and the highest in co-digested cattle manure with non-ensiled straw (Co-dig CM1+Straw_{field}). Mono-digestion of cattle manure reduced the dry matter content by 43 %, while co-digestion with both field- and lab-scale ensiled straw only reduced the dry matter content by 2–4 % compared to non-ensiled straw (Table 2). The decrease in the dry matter following AD was related to the carbon content decrease, with the most considerable effect observed in digestates with brown juice-assisted ensiled straw (Table 2). Ensiling generally resulted in a reduction of C/N ratios in digestates. The C/N ratio ranged from 4.6 to 11.7, which was relatively lower in ensiled straw and press cake by 1.5–3.6 units (Table 2).

During ensiling, organic acids are produced, which cause the degradation of easily decomposable structural polymers such as carbohydrates into degradable intermediates and enhance biochemical accessibility for enzymatic and microbial attack during AD (Larsen et al., 2017). The enhanced biodegradation of the organic matter during AD influences the dry matter and carbon contents in digestates, influencing its physical and chemical compositions, i.e. C/N and NH₄⁺-N/total

Table 1

Characteristics of raw substrates and silages from field-and lab-scale ensiling used in anaerobic co-digestion with cattle manure (cattle slurry) in continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTR) and batch experiments. Values correspond to means \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$).

Substrate	Dry matter	VS	Ash	pH	C	N	O	S	H	C/N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N
	%	% of DM	% of DM	-	% of DM	% of DM	% of DM	% of DM	% of DM	ratio	mg kg ⁻¹ FM
Straw _{field}	53.8 \pm 0.20	94.6 \pm 0.20	5.4 \pm 0.01	7.89	45.8	0.41	44.7	0.06	6.4	117.0	-
Straw _{fieldsilage}	74.1 \pm 0.08	95.2 \pm 0.13	4.8 \pm 0.04	7.92	42.6	0.40	46.8	0.09	6.7	107.7	120
Straw+B _J _{fieldsilage}	75.1 \pm 0.08	93.5 \pm 0.11	6.5 \pm 0.11	7.81	42.8	0.40	44.9	0.08	6.8	105.8	200
Straw _{lab}	87.7 \pm 0.28	95.2 \pm 0.70	4.8 \pm 0.70	6.67	44.0	0.40	44.9	0.13	6.5	106.4	280
Straw+B _J _{lab}	32.0 \pm 0.63	95.1 \pm 0.01	4.9 \pm 0.01	5.97	42.6	0.55	48.5	0.08	6.9	95.1	160
Straw+B _J _{labsilage}	30.2 \pm 0.29	94.1 \pm 0.27	5.9 \pm 0.03	3.81	44.8	1.02	44.9	0.10	7.4	43.8	400
Press cake	37.1 \pm 0.49	94.7 \pm 3.05	5.3 \pm 3.05	4.38	44.3	2.90	43.2	0.14	7.5	15.4	-
Press cake+B _J _{labsilage}	27.7 \pm 0.05	94.9 \pm 0.03	5.1 \pm 0.03	3.51	46.2	3.04	42.6	0.16	8.0	15.2	-
Substrate	NDF	ADF	Hemicellulose	Cellulose	Lignin	NDSF	Citric acid	Lactic acids	Acetic acid	Total sugars	DM loss
	% of DM	g kg ⁻¹ FM	%								
Straw _{field}	85.6 \pm 0.68	47.1 \pm 1.22	38.5 \pm 0.76	34.1 \pm 0.58	13.0 \pm 4.43	14.4 \pm 0.56	bdl	bdl	bdl	bdl	-
Straw _{fieldsilage}	83.1 \pm 0.43	53.2 \pm 1.59	29.9 \pm 1.07	43.6 \pm 0.61	9.7 \pm 3.93	16.9 \pm 0.36	bdl	bdl	bdl	bdl	15.5
Straw+B _J _{fieldsilage}	81.5 \pm 0.92	52.3 \pm 0.84	29.2 \pm 0.45	43.6 \pm 0.54	8.7 \pm 4.92	18.5 \pm 0.75	bdl	bdl	bdl	bdl	14.4
Straw _{lab}	82.6 \pm 0.90	49.6 \pm 0.17	33.1 \pm 0.71	42.3 \pm 0.27	7.2 \pm 1.46	17.4 \pm 0.75	1.15	bdl	1.95	1.5	-
Straw+B _J _{lab}	82.3 \pm 0.43	50.0 \pm 0.86	32.4 \pm 0.12	42.4 \pm 0.49	7.6 \pm 2.85	17.7 \pm 0.35	0.24	0.74	0.37	3.3	0
Straw+B _J _{labsilage}	74.8 \pm 0.53	45.8 \pm 0.21	29.0 \pm 0.48	38.7 \pm 0.06	7.1 \pm 0.70	25.5 \pm 0.39	bdl	21.3	3.08	1.3	5.6
Press cake	64.0 \pm 0.29	37.2 \pm 2.13	26.9 \pm 0.97	34.5 \pm 0.74	2.7 \pm 2.84	36.0 \pm 0.18	bdl	6.83	1.56	6.6	0
Press cake+B _J _{labsilage}	64.0 \pm 1.79	39.2 \pm 3.56	24.8 \pm 1.24	36.6 \pm 1.31	2.6 \pm 3.99	36.0 \pm 1.15	bdl	-	-	-	4.5

DM = Dry matter, VS = Volatile solids, FM = Fresh matter, NDSF = Neutral detergent soluble fibre, bdl = below detection limit.

N ratios. The lower C/N ratio in digestates signifies a possible higher short-term N availability from the digestates (Webb et al., 2013). There were no changes between co-digested ensiled press cake with brown juice and co-digested non-ensiled press cake, except for changes in total carbon content, which decreased by 4 g kg⁻¹ FM in Co-dig CM2+Press cake+B_J_{labsilage} (Table 2).

The co-digestion of straw with cattle manure slightly improved the NH₄⁺-N/N ratio in the digestates compared to the raw cattle manure (CM1), while mono-digestion of cattle manure 1 (CM1) resulted in the most significant increase of NH₄⁺-N/total N ratio by 13 units. The increase in available nitrogen is attributed to the enhanced mineralisation of organically bound nitrogen, especially from proteins during anaerobic digestion (Møller and Müller, 2012).

Anaerobic digestion reduced total sulphur in mono-digested cattle manure 1 (Dig CM1) by 39 %, while it had an insignificant effect on sulphur losses in ensiled and non-ensiled straw (Table 2). The reduction of sulphur during AD is attributed to the sulphur losses in the form of hydrogen sulphide and sulphide-related volatile compounds in the biogas due to the reduction of the sulfates by sulphate-reducing bacteria and sulphur contained in amino acids (Eriksen et al., 2010; Møller and Müller, 2012). The sulphur losses in manure in this study are consistent with those reported by Fontaine et al. (2020) and Mortensen et al. (2021) in thermophilic anaerobic digestion of manure. Fontaine et al. (2020) similarly reported lower losses of sulphur when manure is co-digested with straw, which they attributed to the low protein content in straw, consistent with our findings. Anaerobic mono-digestion of cattle manure 1 (CM1) significantly reduced the SO₄²⁻-S/S ratio and the ratio was relatively the same in other digestates, with the lowest being in cattle manure co-digested with non-ensiled straw with brown juice (Table 2).

3.3. Effect of ensiling on biochemical methane potential and kinetics

The measured biochemical methane potential (BMP) for ensiled straw was higher than the non-ensiled straw in both lab- and field-scale levels (Table 3). In lab-scale ensiling, the methane yields ranged from 290–329 mL g VS⁻¹, with brown juice-assisted ensiling significantly ($p < 0.001$), increasing CH₄ production by 14 % (Table 3). In field-scale ensiling, the CH₄ production ranged from 280–291 mL g VS⁻¹, with brown juice-assisted ensiling increasing methane yield by 4 % compared to ensiled straw without brown juice, which could be attributed to biomass degradability during ensiling. The positive effect of ensiling on BMP was also consistent with CSTR anaerobic digestion, where there was an increase in average specific methane yield ranging from 4 to 14 % compared to non-ensiled straw (Table 2).

The cumulative methane yield from both lab-and field-scale ensiling was fitted with modified Gompertz and first-order kinetics models (Table 3). The methane production and hydrolysis rates in straw mixed with brown juice were greatly increased by ensiling prior to the batch tests. For instance, brown juice-assisted ensiling at the lab-scale level significantly increased CH₄ production rate (μ_m) by 24 % and the hydrolysis rate (k) by 8 % compared to non-ensiled straw (Table 3).

In CSTR anaerobic digestion, the total VFA were higher in the first weeks of AD, then afterwards, the concentration of VFA started to decline gradually till the last day of digestion, with the lowest levels recorded in mono-digested raw cattle manure 1 (Figure S4). The pH was relatively stable throughout the AD despite feeding silage with low pH in some reactors, ranging from 7.65 to 8.04 (Figure S5). This could be ascribed to the high buffering capacity of the manure used in the co-digestion. The corrected methane content in biogas from co-digestion of substrates was > 55 %, with the highest CH₄ content observed in mono-digested cattle manure 1 (Dig CM1) at 63 % CH₄ (Figure S6).

Table 2

Chemical properties of the digestates from continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTR) and raw cattle manures used in the soil incubation experiment. Values correspond to means and standard deviation in brackets (n = 3).

Material	Dry matter	Volatile solids	Ash	pH	Total N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	Total C	Total S	SO ₄ ²⁻ -S	C/N	C/S	N/S	CH ₄ yield	SO ₄ ²⁻ -S	(SO ₄ ²⁻ -S + S ²⁻ -S)/S
	% of FM	% of DM	% of DM	-	g kg ⁻¹ FM	%	g kg ⁻¹ FM	g kg ⁻¹ FM	g kg ⁻¹ FM	ratio	ratio	ratio	NL kg VS ⁻¹	%	%
Digestates from field-scale ensiling experiment															
Cattle Manure 1 (CM1)	6.18 (0.09)	78.6 (0.35)	21.4 (0.35)	7.34	2.77 (0.03)	49.1	25.2 (0.72)	0.36 (0.009)	0.063	9.1	70.1	7.7	-	17.5	30.0
Digested CM1	3.51 (0.02)	69.1 (0.30)	30.9 (0.30)	8.07	2.79 (0.01)	62.2	13.3 (0.21)	0.22 (0.005)	0.011	4.8	59.6	12.5	209 (5.0)	4.9	8.7
Co-dig CM1+Straw _{field}	7.19 (0.06)	82.4 (0.33)	17.6 (0.33)	7.64	2.81 (0.08)	54.0	22.9 (0.99)	0.28 (0.006)	0.011	8.2	82.4	10.1	179 (3.6)	4.0	8.5
Co-dig CM1+Straw _{fieldsilage}	6.96 (0.03)	80.5 (0.07)	19.5 (0.07)	7.76	3.00 (0.05)	54.3	18.7 (0.38)	0.26 (0.009)	0.012	6.2	72.3	11.6	186 (2.4)	4.6	10.0
Co-dig CM1+Straw+BJ _{fieldsilage}	7.04 (0.14)	80.2 (0.56)	19.8 (0.56)	7.80	2.97 (0.03)	54.4	13.6 (0.26)	0.23 (0.009)	0.012	4.6	58.1	12.7	190 (3.2)	5.1	10.7
Digestates from Lab-scale ensiling experiment															
Cattle manure 2 (CM2)	6.73 (0.13)	80.3 (0.52)	19.7 (0.52)	6.94	2.50 (0.02)	45.3	28.8 (0.27)	0.38 (0.007)	0.045	11.5	76.4	6.6	-	11.9	24.9
Co-dig CM2+Straw+BJ _{lab}	7.09 (0.20)	83.0 (0.32)	17.0 (0.32)	7.48	2.52 (0.06)	51.1	29.6 (0.45)	0.33 (0.006)	0.012	11.7	89.6	7.6	196 (9.0)	3.6	8.2
Co-dig CM2+straw+BJ _{absilage}	6.85 (0.17)	81.6 (0.22)	18.4 (0.22)	7.48	2.58 (0.03)	51.1	20.3 (0.71)	0.34 (0.021)	0.015	7.9	59.5	7.6	204 (9.9)	4.4	8.3
Co-dig CM2+Press cake	5.33 (0.10)	76.6 (0.15)	23.4 (0.15)	7.59	3.17 (0.03)	47.6	20.2 (0.25)	0.31 (0.005)	0.013	6.4	66.2	10.4	216 (9.0)	4.3	12.4
Co-dig CM2+Press cake+BJ _{absilage}	5.34 (0.04)	76.7 (0.14)	23.3 (0.14)	7.57	3.26 (0.03)	48.6	16.0 (0.21)	0.33 (0.008)	0.013	4.9	49.0	10.0	221 (7.2)	4.0	11.3

Co-dig = co-digested, DM = dry matter, FM = fresh matter, BJ = brown juice. The specific methane yield is the average yield in the last hydraulic retention time of 25 days in the CSTR AD experiment.

The observed positive effects of brown juice-assisted ensiling of straw compared to an addition of brown juice to straw without ensiling at the lab-scale level on CH₄ yields, the rate of CH₄ production and the hydrolysis rate could be attributed to the enhanced production of volatile fatty acids and other organic acids during the ensiling process. Sieborg et al. (2020) and Sun et al. (2022) reported similar effects of ensiling and co-ensiling of biomass on biogas yields. Therefore, ensiling and brown juice-assisted ensiling can potentially improve energy production from the straw. The improved CH₄ production rate (mL g VS⁻¹ d⁻¹) and hydrolysis rate could make commercial biogas plants economically viable as they operate in low retention times (Larsen et al., 2017).

Management is critical in influencing dry matter and energy losses in silage at filling and feed-out phases (Villa et al., 2020). The unexpectedly low maximum methane production (μm) and hydrolysis rates in field-scale ensiled straw could be attributed to the losses of some VFA and organic compounds just prior to AD associated with sampling and chopping and biomass spoilage during the ensiling period, as explained earlier. Moreover, the relatively higher dry matter content of the straw prior to the ensiling process might have made the ensiling process inefficient, resulting to poor quality of silage and hence low methane yields. An initial dry matter content of 28–40 % of the substrates is ideal for the optimal ensiling process. However, the required dry matter may depend on the feedstock type and its chemical properties (Villa et al., 2020). The extended period of field-scale ensiling compared to lab-scale ensiling did not positively influence the methane yield. A related study by Ai et al. (2019) reported a significant reduction in biogas yield after ten months of ensiling straw, which they attributed to spoilage of silage due to secondary fermentation, which reduced VFAs.

The differences in the BMP of straw used in the field- and lab-scale ensiling experiment could also be explained by differences in straw quality and their management prior to anaerobic digestion. For instance, the straw was sourced from two different farms, and straw from field-scale ensiling was chopped before AD, affecting its contents and the ultimate biogas yield. These differences may limit the comparison of different pre-treatment technologies and comparisons with other studies. However, in our study, the BMP of the straw ranged from 243 to 278 NL CH₄ kg⁻¹ VS (Figure S3), which is within the range for straws, as summarised by Larsen et al. (2017).

3.4. Effects of ensiling and anaerobic digestion on manure N turnover in soil

The soil inorganic N dynamics, as affected by the ensiling with or without brown juice and anaerobic digestion of substrates, was followed for 80 days after digestate application. Ensiling of substrates was generally found to increase net available inorganic N in the soil compared to non-ensiled substrates, whereas ensiling with or without brown juice did not influence the net inorganic N release in the soil after 80 days of incubation.

On day 0, the soil NH₄⁺-N increased with digestate application, with 94 % of the applied NH₄⁺-N recovered in a reference treatment applied with ammonium sulphate (Figure S2). However, on day 2 of incubation, the net inorganic N release decreased in the two raw cattle manures, CM1 and CM2 (Fig. 2), probably due to microbial immobilisation of N due to carbon assimilation associated with the decomposition of high volatile fatty acids content present in the raw cattle manures (Kirchmann and Lundvall, 1993; Sørensen, 1998). All the digestates had a higher net inorganic N release in the soil after two days of application, with no N immobilisation observed (Table 4).

After day two, the net inorganic N release in soil (% of applied N) started to increase gradually until the end of the incubation period, except for digestate derived from non-ensiled straw (Co-dig CM1+straw_{field}), which exhibited a slight

Table 3

Biochemical methane potential (BMP) and kinetic parameters from a batch experiment with ensiled and non-ensiled wheat straw under lab- and field-scale conditions fitted with modified Gompertz and first-order kinetics models. Values correspond to means ± standard error (n = 3).

Treatments	Modified Gompertz model					First-order model				
	BMP mL g VS ⁻¹	B ₀ mL g VS ⁻¹	μ _m mL g VS ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	R ² -	RMSE -	B ₀ mL g VS ⁻¹	k day	R ² -	RMSE -	
Straw _{Lab}	290.2 ± 4.7 ^a	265.3 ± 3.9 ^{ab}	11.8 ± 0.22 ^{bc}	0.98	14.83	291.3 ± 3.7 ^{ab}	0.051 ± 0.0 ^{ab}	0.98	13.77	
Straw+BJ _{lab}	287.8 ± 3.3 ^a	266.6 ± 4.7 ^{ab}	11.9 ± 0.02 ^c	0.98	13.37	291.8 ± 4.0 ^{ab}	0.051 ± 0.0 ^{ab}	0.98	13.83	
Straw+BJ _{lab} silage	329.9 ± 3.4 ^b	297.2 ± 1.9 ^b	14.6 ± 0.16 ^d	0.98	17.07	325.7 ± 1.8 ^b	0.055 ± 0.0 ^b	0.98	16.47	
Straw _{Field}	280.7 ± 7.3 ^a	249.3 ± 5.1 ^a	10.1 ± 0.38 ^{ab}	0.92	22.74	249.6 ± 4.5 ^a	0.092 ± 0.0 ^c	0.95	17.87	
Straw _{field} silage	281.0 ± 14.3 ^a	258.0 ± 14.9 ^{ab}	10.5 ± 0.07 ^{abc}	0.97	15.62	284.2 ± 12.0 ^{ab}	0.047 ± 0.0 ^{ab}	0.98	13.87	
Straw+BJ _{field} silage	291.0 ± 11.8 ^a	270.9 ± 15.4 ^{ab}	9.7 ± 0.50 ^a	0.97	16.56	297.8 ± 13.2 ^b	0.043 ± 0.0 ^a	0.98	12.75	

The letters indicate significant differences calculated by pairwise comparisons between averages of the treatments (n = 3). Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different (p < 0.05).

Fig. 2. Net inorganic N release related to total N application in soil amended with raw cattle manure and digestates. (a) digestates from a co-digestion (Co-dig) of cattle manure (CM1) with ensiled and non-ensiled straw in the field-scale level with or without brown juice (BJ), (b) digestates from a co-digestion of cattle manure (CM2) with ensiled and non-ensiled press cake; non-ensiled straw with brown juice and brown juice assisted-ensiled straw at the lab-scale level. The inorganic N in a control soil was subtracted to calculate the net inorganic N release in the soil. Error bars indicate standard deviation (n = 3).

decline over time, probably due to N immobilisation by soil microbial biomass (Fig. 2 and Table 4). At day 28, nearly all NH₄⁺-N was converted to NO₃⁻-N due to nitrification, where it remained relatively constant until the end of the incubation experiment (Figure S2).

After 80 days of incubation, mono-digested cattle manure (Dig CM1) had the highest net inorganic N release in the soil at 66 % (% of N input), while co-digested cattle manure with non-ensiled straw at field scale had the lowest net inorganic N release (% of N input) at 44 %. Anaerobic mono-digestion of cattle manure significantly (p < 0.001) increased the net inorganic N release in soil by 17 % units (% of N input). The co-digestion of manure with ensiled straw increased the net inorganic N release (% of N input) in the range of 1 to 6 % units relative to the raw cattle manures (Fig. 2).

Ensiling of straw at both lab- and field scales generally increased the net inorganic N release in the soil compared to non-ensiled straw (Table 4). At the field-scale level, ensiling of straw increased net inorganic N release in the soil in the range of 11 to 15 mg N kg⁻¹ soil, whereas at the lab-scale level, the increase was around 6 mg N kg⁻¹ soil (Fig. 2, Table 4). The use of brown juice as an additive in ensiling of straw did not influence the net inorganic N release in soil. Applying digestates derived from non-ensiled straw led to a lower net inorganic N release in the soil by up to 5 % compared to the raw cattle manure (Table 4). Amendment of soil with press cake-derived digestates, ensiled and non-ensiled, resulted in the highest net inorganic N release in the soil in the range of 53 to 54 % (% of N input), with an increase of 11 % units when related to the raw cattle manure 2.

The pH of the soils increased by 0.96 units on average immediately after amendment with digestates, whereas amendment with raw cattle manure increased the soil pH by 0.31 units (Table S3). Afterwards, the pH gradually dropped until the end of the experiment, which could be explained by the NH₄⁺ -N nitrification into NO₃⁻ -N over time (Sørensen, 1998).

The increased net inorganic N release in soil from the digestates, especially mono-digested cattle manure, could be attributed to the enhanced organic N mineralisation and organic matter decomposition during the anaerobic digestion of the cattle manure (Møller and Müller, 2012). Conversely, higher net inorganic N release from digestates derived from ensiled straw compared to the non-ensiled straw could be attributed to the improved hydrolysis step of the AD process due to the biological pre-treatment effect caused by ensiling of straw. For instance, the improved hydrolysis step could enhance N solubilisation from substrates through protein hydrolysis, increasing the digestate's fertiliser value. Moreover, this study shows that the straw's pre-treatment effect influences biochemical properties such as the C/N ratio as more carbon is recovered as biogas (CH₄ + CO₂). The changes influence microbial and extracellular enzymatic activities, accelerating further digestate decomposition in the soil after incorporation and possibly reducing N immobilisation, subsequently enhancing further nutrient release.

High net N mineralisation, 30 to 39 mg N kg⁻¹ soil, in press cake-derived digestates after soil incorporation could be explained by the fact that during crude protein extraction in the biorefinery process, fibre-bound proteins and other nitrogenous compounds are still left in the press cake (Santamaria-Fernandez et al., 2020). This implies that the organically bound nitrogen in the press cake could be recovered and potentially re-circulated back to the field in a readily available NH₄⁺-N form through anaerobic digestion. Santamaria-Fernandez et al. (2020) recovered 61%–78% of the N input and other nutrients in press cake and brown juice after crude protein extraction from grass, with only 3 to 16% of nutrients removed in the protein concentrate. The differences in the mineralisation kinetics in straw and press cake digestates could be attributed to the substrate's characteristics. Straw is recalcitrant for degradation due to its high C/N ratio whereas press cake was derived from grass-clover whose degradation is relatively faster and is characterised by a lower C/N ratio (Table 2).

The net inorganic N release after 80 days of incubation was negatively and strongly correlated with the C/N ratio of the digestates ($r = -0.72$; $p < 0.001$), whereas it was positively and strongly correlated with NH₄⁺-N/total N ratio in digestates ($r = 0.66$; $p < 0.001$). Additionally, the net inorganic N release was positively and strongly correlated with NDSF ($r = 0.66$; $p = 0.024$) and negatively and strongly corrected with hemicellulose content ($r = -0.74$; $p = 0.004$). The observed high correlations could be used to predict the N dynamics and availability following the application of digestates to the soil, and these findings corroborate with previous studies (Fontaine et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Nyang'au et al., 2022, 2023).

3.5. Effect of ensiling and anaerobic digestion on inorganic S dynamics and availability in soil

Sulphur from organic fertilisers is applied in both organic forms (sulphur directly bonded to C and ester S) and inorganic forms (sulphate and sulphide), but plants mainly take up S in inorganic form (Kertesz and Mirleau, 2004). The net release of mineral S in soil from raw cattle manure 1 was significantly reduced after anaerobic digestion, which could be explained by the loss of mineral sulphur during the digestion (Møller and Müller, 2012). After the application of untreated and mono-digested cattle slurry, the net inorganic S release remained nearly similar at day 0 and day 80 but with some fluctuations during the period of incubation (Fig. 3).

All the digestates from the co-digestion with straw or press cake showed a steady decline in mineral S release in the soil after the first few days, where there was a short-lived increase in mineral S (Fig. 3, Table S2). The gradual increase of inorganic S release in the first days of digestate incorporation could be explained by the gross S mineralisation due to intense microbial activities caused by adding degradable organic matter into the soil. The microorganisms cause enzymatic hydrolysis of organic sulfates present in digestates during the oxidation of carbon, causing the release of inorganic sulfates (Eriksen, 2005; McGill and Cole, 1981). A similar trend was reported by Blum et al. (2013) and Solomon et al. (2011) who found an increase in ester sulfates in the initial stages of plant material decomposition in soil.

The decline in the inorganic S release could be attributed to sulphur immobilisation (Eriksen, 2005). After the digestates application, microbial activities are stimulated due to recalcitrant materials in the digestates. Microbial activities cause assimilatory reduction of sulfates in the digestates as the primary S supply source for biomass build-up (Eriksen, 2005), limiting the net inorganic S release to the soil. The immobilised S by the microbial biomass is ultimately transformed into a soil organic S pool, making it unavailable for the next crop (Eriksen, 1997). The generally low levels of inorganic S in digestates from the co-digested straw, compared to mono-digested cattle manure, could be attributed to the low protein content in straw (Fontaine et al., 2020).

Table 4

Average concentration of inorganic N (mg N kg^{-1} soil) measured in the soil during the 80 days of incubation at 10°C . The soil was amended with two batches of raw cattle manure (cattle slurry) with distinct characteristics (CM1 and CM2), digested cattle manure 1 (Dig CM1) and digestates from a co-digestion (co-dig) of cattle manures with ensiled straw, non-ensiled straw and the press cake from the field- and lab-scale ensiling experiments with or without brown juice. The control represents unamended soil. Values correspond to means \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$).

Material	Days after application						
	0	2	7	14	28	50	80
Digestates from field-scale ensiling experiment							
Control	$25.4 \pm 0.78^{\text{a}}$	$26.1 \pm 0.32^{\text{a}}$	$26.3 \pm 0.21^{\text{a}}$	$26.6 \pm 0.17^{\text{a}}$	$27.7 \pm 0.64^{\text{a}}$	$29.4 \pm 0.06^{\text{a}}$	$32.6 \pm 0.99^{\text{a}}$
Cattle Manure 1 (CM1)	$113.9 \pm 7.64^{\text{bc}}$	$79.5 \pm 0.52^{\text{b}}$	$97.6 \pm 1.40^{\text{b}}$	$108.6 \pm 9.02^{\text{b}}$	$112.5 \pm 5.82^{\text{b}}$	$119.3 \pm 2.43^{\text{b}}$	$130.2 \pm 1.90^{\text{c}}$
Digested CM1	$141.8 \pm 13.83^{\text{c}}$	$136.4 \pm 2.26^{\text{c}}$	$145.4 \pm 2.13^{\text{d}}$	$145.3 \pm 1.70^{\text{d}}$	$148.6 \pm 2.14^{\text{e}}$	$155.6 \pm 2.69^{\text{d}}$	$163.6 \pm 1.41^{\text{d}}$
Co-dig CM1+Straw _{field}	$105.7 \pm 1.91^{\text{b}}$	$123.5 \pm 3.18^{\text{c}}$	$128.4 \pm 2.91^{\text{c}}$	$125.3 \pm 3.47^{\text{c}}$	$116.6 \pm 1.99^{\text{bc}}$	$116.9 \pm 6.20^{\text{b}}$	$120.1 \pm 6.47^{\text{b}}$
Co-dig CM1+Straw _{fieldsilage}	$122.0 \pm 11.99^{\text{b}}$	$134.5 \pm 5.89^{\text{de}}$	$130.4 \pm 1.43^{\text{c}}$	$129.9 \pm 1.11^{\text{c}}$	$125.3 \pm 1.45^{\text{cd}}$	$124.6 \pm 1.55^{\text{bc}}$	$135.3 \pm 0.26^{\text{c}}$
Co-dig CM1+Straw+BJ _{fieldsilage}	$121.4 \pm 13.51^{\text{bc}}$	$126.2 \pm 2.33^{\text{cd}}$	$129.0 \pm 1.56^{\text{c}}$	$127.5 \pm 1.12^{\text{c}}$	$128.2 \pm 4.66^{\text{d}}$	$129.2 \pm 0.99^{\text{c}}$	$131.5 \pm 1.30^{\text{c}}$
Digestates from Lab-scale ensiling experiment							
Control	$25.4 \pm 0.78^{\text{A}}$	$26.1 \pm 0.32^{\text{A}}$	$26.3 \pm 0.21^{\text{A}}$	$26.6 \pm 0.17^{\text{A}}$	$27.7 \pm 0.64^{\text{A}}$	$29.4 \pm 0.06^{\text{A}}$	$32.6 \pm 0.99^{\text{A}}$
Cattle manure 2 (CM2)	$103.9 \pm 4.86^{\text{B}}$	$73.8 \pm 1.69^{\text{B}}$	$85.3 \pm 1.37^{\text{B}}$	$88.7 \pm 1.53^{\text{B}}$	$102.1 \pm 2.78^{\text{B}}$	$107.2 \pm 2.39^{\text{B}}$	$117.5 \pm 3.11^{\text{B}}$
Co-dig CM2+Straw+BJ _{lab}	$121.4 \pm 10.61^{\text{B}}$	$122.2 \pm 2.75^{\text{DE}}$	$120.2 \pm 2.59^{\text{CD}}$	$119.6 \pm 2.75^{\text{C}}$	$119.6 \pm 1.63^{\text{CD}}$	$122.3 \pm 4.07^{\text{C}}$	$123.3 \pm 1.66^{\text{BC}}$
Co-dig CM2+Straw+BJ _{labsilage}	$120.4 \pm 10.29^{\text{B}}$	$124.2 \pm 3.85^{\text{E}}$	$128.1 \pm 6.66^{\text{D}}$	$126.9 \pm 1.89^{\text{C}}$	$120.6 \pm 1.72^{\text{C}}$	$122.1 \pm 1.01^{\text{C}}$	$129.6 \pm 0.28^{\text{CD}}$
Co-dig CM2+Press cake	$109.7 \pm 11.72^{\text{B}}$	$110.7 \pm 8.29^{\text{CD}}$	$115.3 \pm 3.65^{\text{C}}$	$118.3 \pm 3.01^{\text{C}}$	$125.9 \pm 0.87^{\text{DE}}$	$130.3 \pm 1.72^{\text{D}}$	$139.3 \pm 4.17^{\text{D}}$
Co-dig CM2+Press cake+BJ _{labsilage}	$99.5 \pm 13.86^{\text{B}}$	$108.4 \pm 3.56^{\text{C}}$	$118.7 \pm 4.21^{\text{CD}}$	$121.4 \pm 6.06^{\text{C}}$	$127.1 \pm 1.07^{\text{E}}$	$132.5 \pm 1.45^{\text{D}}$	$138.3 \pm 3.97^{\text{D}}$

The letters indicate significant differences calculated by pairwise comparisons between averages of the treatments on each day ($n = 3$). Means followed by different letters within each column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Small letters indicate differences among field-scale digestates, while differences in lab-scale derived digestates are indicated by capital letters.

Ensiling of straw significantly affected the net inorganic S release in the soil after 80 days of incubation. Field-scale ensiling of straw, with or without brown juice, prior to anaerobic digestion resulted in a net positive inorganic S release in the soil in the range of 3 to 5 % units higher compared to non-ensiled straw, hence reducing inorganic S immobilisation, while for lab-scale ensiling, brown juice-assisted straw ensiling reduced S immobilisation by 7 % units when related to non-ensiled straw.

The low net inorganic S release in the soil from non-ensiled straw mixed with brown juice indicated that brown juice alone did not influence S availability in digestates (Fig. 3). Likewise, ensiling of press cake with brown juice before digestion did not influence the net inorganic S release in the soil (Fig. 3). As explained earlier, the significant effect ($p < 0.001$) of ensiling on inorganic S release in the soil could be attributed to the enhanced degradation of the straw structural polysaccharides during the ensiling process by the organic acids formed. As a result, the biochemical accessibility of substrate is increased, which increases the solubilisation of soluble sulfates and increases the concentration of degradable organic S in the digestates, making them readily available in the soil for plant uptake after digestate application.

The chemical properties of the digestates could largely explain the net inorganic S release in the soil. The high proportion of $\text{SO}_4^{2-}\text{-S/S}$ and $(\text{SO}_4^{2-}\text{-S} + \text{S}^{2-}\text{-S})/\text{S}$ in the digestates would imply high net inorganic S release to the soil as indicated by strong positive correlations with net inorganic S release of $r = 0.82$; $p < 0.001$ and $r = 0.78$; $p < 0.001$ (Fig. 4). In contrast, the inorganic S immobilisation could be linked to the lignocellulosic nature of the biomass used as an input in the biogas plant. For instance, cellulose content was negatively and strongly correlated with net inorganic S release in the soil after 80 days of incubation ($r = -0.73$; $p = 0.004$). Moreover, the lignin and C/S ratios in the digestates negatively correlated with the net inorganic S release in the soil. The high lignin content limits accessibility to organic esters during decomposition, affecting S mineralisation (Eriksen, 2005).

3.6. Practical perspectives

Straw is lignocellulosic biomass with high fibre content, limiting its degradation during anaerobic digestion. Moreover, the digestion of straw poses problems with pumping and stirring, which require investments in rebuilding and adapting the biogas plants to handle the high dry matter content in solid biomasses (Møller and Nielsen, 2016). With an increasing shift towards utilising solid biomass in commercial biogas plants, where substrates are loaded within a short HRT, it makes it impossible to completely degrade lignocellulosic biomass, resulting in increasing quantities of dry matter content in digestates. This consequently results in poor nitrogen utilisation from the digestates. One of the strategies to improve the degradation of such lignocellulosic biomasses during anaerobic digestion is through ensiling, which is an economical pre-treatment technique despite being slow. Ensiling of the biomass provides an option to preserve the biomass during a variable storage time; at the same time, it improves the AD process by causing a biological pre-treatment effect during the ensiling period (Franco et al., 2016).

Fig. 3. Net inorganic S release in soil related to total S application in soil amended with raw cattle manure and digestates. (a) digestates from a co-digestion (Co-dig) of cattle manure (CM1) with ensiled and non-ensiled straw in the field-scale level with or without brown juice (BJ), (b) digestates from a co-digestion of cattle manure (CM2) with ensiled and non-ensiled press cake; non-ensiled straw with brown juice and brown juice assisted-ensiled straw at the lab-scale level. Inorganic S in a control soil was subtracted to calculate the percentage of net inorganic S released in the soil. Small letters indicate differences among field-scale digestates, while differences in lab-scale digestates are indicated by capital letters. Error bars represent standard errors (n = 3).

Fig. 4. Correlations between net inorganic S release in soil after 80 days of incubation related to total S application with the digestates and sulphate-S ((SO₄²⁻-S)/S), sulphate-S + sulphide-S ((SO₄²⁻-S+S²⁻-S)/S) and cellulose content of digestates.

Our study revealed that applying co-digested non-ensiled straw with cattle manure results in a net negative nitrogen effect compared to raw cattle manure alone, making it impractical for farmers to apply digestates derived from co-digestion of lignocellulosic agricultural residuals such as straw. On the other hand, the net inorganic N release was positively increased by ensiling the straw prior to anaerobic co-digestion with cattle manure. The study also revealed that the ensiling of straw tended to increase methane yields and rate of methane production, and at the same time, it proved to be a favourable way of reducing sulphur immobilisation after digestate application. However, to fully benefit from biomass ensiling on methane yield and nutrient availability, organic acid and volatile solid losses during ensiling and silage handling until feeding into AD plants ought to be minimised.

The study demonstrates that alternative utilisation of press cake and brown juice from crude protein extraction in biorefinery for biogas production may improve nutrient recovery and increase biogas production, making the whole process sustainable and closing the nutrient and material cycles. Nevertheless, there are practical issues regarding storing, handling and transporting large quantities of brown juice to fields far away from biorefinery plants, making the process uneconomical. Hence, it may be more relevant to apply the brown juice to the straw and ensile the mixture in clamps or silos close to the biorefinery plants or at the biogas plant.

Furthermore, our study shows that co-digestion of press cake derived from a grass-clover mixture resulted in higher soil N availability and high net N mineralisation after soil application compared to ensiled and non-ensiled straws. The use of brown juice as an additive in ensiling improved the silage quality in the lab-scale ensiling of straw due to its low pH level and high sugar content, making it a potential good fermentation stimulator in silage making.

4. Conclusions

This study shows that ensiling of straw acts as a pre-treatment method, which enhances straw biodegradation through increased biochemical accessibility during anaerobic digestion. Lab-scale ensiling of straw resulted in minimal loss of biomass during ensiling and significantly increased methane yields and methane production rates, whereas ensiling under field conditions had no clear effect on the following methane production. Ensiling of straw prior to digestion increased the net inorganic N release from digestates in soil, attributed to enhanced increased biochemical accessibility and nutrient solubilisation during the anaerobic digestion process. Moreover, it greatly reduced net inorganic sulphur immobilisation in the soil. Despite our results showing strong evidence of the positive effect of ensiling on the N and S availability from the digestates following their application to soil, the synergistic effects of brown juice as an ensiling additive were insignificant. To improve field scale ensiling of straw, we recommend adding higher doses of brown juices and water to achieve dry matter content of 30–35 % before ensiling, chopping straw into smaller pieces to have higher packing density and proper silage management prior to feeding the biogas reactors. Future research should compare ensiling with other pre-treatment techniques regarding their effects on the nutrient availability of biomass prior to anaerobic digestion.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jared Onyango Nyang'au: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Henrik Bjarne Møller:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Søren Ugilt Larsen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Peter Sørensen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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